

VillageMath Educational Review

An International/Multidisciplinary Journal of
Network for Grassroots Science and Mathematics
Education (The VillageMath Network)

A publication of VillageMath Educational Services
(CAC RC: 4097888)

Volume 7, Issue 1

May, 2025

CODEN: VERIAU

Perceived Influence of Cultural Beliefs on Students' Academic Performance in Physics in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15342442>

Article History: Received 3rd April, 2025; Revised 1st May, 2025; Published 5th May, 2025.

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How to Cite this Article:

Taangahar, B. A., Fiase, G. A., & Zever, J. A. (2025). Perceived Influence of Cultural Beliefs on Students' Academic Performance in Science in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. *VillageMath Educational Review (VER)*, 7(1), 28-37.

<https://ngsme.villagemath.net/journals/ver/v7i1/taangahar-fiase-zever>

Abstract

This research examined the influence of perceived students' cultural beliefs on their science performance in secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area (LGA) of Benue State, Nigeria using descriptive survey design. The sample comprises a total of 116 students in intact classes (66 males and 50 females) representing 13% of the population of 900 secondary two students in 21 grant-aided schools in the LGA. Four co-educational schools were purposively sampled in order to make use of both male and female students. Three research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. Perception of Student's Cultural Belief Questionnaire (PSCBQ) was researcher-developed and used for data collection. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.62 established through Cronbach Alpha

method. The data was analyzed using mean scores for the research questions and t-test for the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings were that students agreed that the stated cultural practices are perceived by them, yielding a high mean (3.38) and that perceived cultural belief influence students' performance in science to a high extent (3.19). The mean of the influence of perceived cultural beliefs between male and female students' performance in science was 3.20 for males and 3.23 for females. This provided the mean difference of 0.03 which was found to be non-significant. It was concluded that students that perceived cultural beliefs influence their performance in science. It was recommended that more awareness should be created to the students by science teachers so as to reduce the negative effect of cultural beliefs on their performance in science.

Keywords: Cultural Beliefs, Academic Performance, Perception, Science Education, Science Misconception

Introduction

Nigeria is endowed with diverse ethnic groups having different cultural beliefs. These beliefs could consist attitude, norms and values which people in a particular group share, as well as the way they think, relate and learn. This suggests that cognitive activities are influenced as they occur within a cultural setting, with each group having its distinct cultural inclinations. Some inclinations aid while others inhibit the students' cognition in the study of science.

There are a variety of characteristics that make up a cultural group. Each cultural group is unique in a community with unity of purpose. It is likely to have a common history, location as well as a totemic ancestor. A cultural group shares a common language, belief and cultural practices. These practices may include taboos that might hinder children's study of science.

According to Adeniran and Yaapera (2019), students who come from a socio-cultural background, different from those of their teachers, may have values, goals and interest that are accepted to their community but not to the school community. Students with cultural orientation based on nonfactual opinions and beliefs would reject certain scientific claims because they go contrary to their beliefs. Audu (2021) opined that the perception students have on various cultural practices could have great effects on students' performance in science.

Perception could be the way one sees something. Perception is the ability to see, hear or become aware of something through the senses (Agogo & Onda, 2014). Schools are some of the places where children from different cultures interact with one another, this interaction may either enhance or reduce students understanding of science concepts due to their cultural diversity.

Some of the perceived cultural practices identified in the literature include a belief that traditional medicine should be prepared and taken using the left hand only and that metal or glassware should not be used but with clay pots or calabashes. Failure to do so the medicine might lose its potency. Such beliefs hamper students' participation in the chemical sciences. Also, it is believed that sweeping in the night means that one is sweeping away his success or prosperity (Adeniran & Yaapera, 2019).

Again, the culture diagnosis of illness is usually associated with witchcraft and charm. Children who come from terrains that could have been used for field tips to explore real life studies are afraid of natural resources like streams, rivers, forests, hills and mountains. This is especially when they are termed sacred and associated with myth and superstition (Ode, Iloazksis & Oholiab, 2020). Again, the owl is considered nocturnal and should only be seen in the night. When sighted during the daytime, some cultures interpret it to mean somebody will die. These beliefs create fear and dislike for science when they are used as specimens in science practical lessons. Again, the taboo on restriction of children from mentioning sex organs could hinder their participation in the biological sciences where these concepts are taught (Adeniran & Yaapera, 2019).

The suspicion that science education is an introduction of western culture in Africa has occasioned resistance due to its seemingly diametrically opposed beliefs to African tradition. Whereas science education is anchored on the assumptions that all events in nature, are to a certain degree, ordered, regular, predictable and lawful, African traditions are largely based on visions and beliefs (Taangahar, 2017). Generally, Science has revolutionized the way people understand natural phenomena due to its insistence on certain values which are different from norms and values of tradition (Fatoki & Taangahar, 2019). Science at secondary school level is compartmentalized into physics, chemistry and biology with mathematics as the “mother of sciences” (Kangaroo, 2017). These areas are populated by both male and female students who have earned their placement in science at the senior secondary level.

Gender roles are likely to affect how students think about science in relation to their traditional role stereotype based on beliefs, myths and taboos. Culture components that determine people's attitude towards achievement in science consist of linguistic, social, political, economic, religion and gender aspects. Cultural practices thought to affect female students in science and science related careers include the prevention of females from getting close to dead animals or corpses, as it is believed to prevent them from bearing male children, which is not in line with scientific beliefs (Taangahar & Ameh, 2017). This might impede their handling of specimens in science practical lessons where dead animals are preserved and used as specimens. Most gender roles are determined by society. Society determines what is expected of individuals. These expectations, in Nigeria, are essentially influenced by cultural practices. The belief that prohibits children from mentioning sexual reproductive organs is thought to be gender biased.

Performance could be described as attainment of quantifiable objectives. It is not only what people achieve but how they achieve it. It could be high or low. A high-performance result comes from appropriate behavior and effective use of required knowledge, skills and competences. The failure to meet these requirements may automatically reflect low performance. In managing performance, one must examine how results are attained because this provides the information necessary to consider what needs to be done to improve those results. Performance could be expressed by both behaviors and results. Behavior is seen to emanate from performance and could transform performance from abstraction to action. Behavior is not just the instrument for assessing results but also an outcome of a people's

culture (Brumbach, Figueredo & Ellis, 2009). The product of mental and physical effort applied to tasks, to a large extent, depends on the cultural practices of a people.

The general outcry with respect to the allegedly persistent underachievement in science among senior secondary school students has reached an alarming rate. This worrisome development has been left for too long and has begun to prompt research to establish the causal variable for the repeated failures of students in science. One common variable is whether cultural practices have inhibited the learning of science. It is suspected that if this is not addressed it may deal an adverse blow on students' performance in science. Thus, there is need to identify the cultural beliefs that science students bring into classes and whether these beliefs differ between the male and female students. This is the problem addressed by this present investigation.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- i. What are perceived cultural beliefs that influence students' performance in science in secondary schools?
- ii. What is the influence of perceived cultural beliefs on students' performance in science?
- iii. What is the difference in the influence of perceived cultural beliefs on male and female science students' performance?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis is formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. H_0 : Influence of perceived cultural beliefs on students' performance do not significantly differ between male and female students.

Methodology

Descriptive-survey research design was used for this study. Survey is suitable since the needed information existed in the population without manipulation of any treatment. The study area was Makurdi Local Government Area. The choice for this area was based on the fact that there are rich cultural practices with much poor performance of students in science in the area. The study population consists of 900 senior secondary two students in 21 grant-aided schools. Four co-educational schools were purposively sampled in order to make use of both male and female students. A total of 116 students in intact classes made up the sample (66 males and 50 females), representing 13% of the population.

The instrument for data collection used for the study is a researcher-developed questionnaire titled: Perception of Student's Cultural Belief Questionnaire (PSCBQ). The questionnaire consists three sections: Section A sought demographic information about the respondents as to whether they were male or female. Section B required the respondents to determine the cultural beliefs students bring into science classes. Section C dealt with the influence of the students' perceived cultural beliefs on their performance in science. Section D sought to determine the influence of perception of students' cultural beliefs on their performance in science. It used a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

The PSCBQ was given to two senior lecturers in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria to do face and content validation. The expert advice and suggestions were strictly adhered to before the instrument was administered on the respondents.

The reliability of the instrument was carried out on 30 senior secondary school students who were not used for the main study. Thirty questionnaires were distributed to the students by the researchers and collected after they were completed. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha to obtain reliability which yielded a coefficient of 0.62. This shows that the instrument was reliable to be used for the study. Coefficient of 0.5 and above, according to Cronbach and Meehl (1955), is considered reliable.

Permission was obtained from principals of sampled schools before the administration of the questionnaire. The data collected was analyzed using mean scores for the research questions and t-test for the hypothesis.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to research questions and hypothesis.

Research Question One

What are perceived cultural beliefs that influence students' performance in science in secondary schools?

Table 1: Mean Score and Standard Deviation for Students' Cultural Beliefs in Science in Secondary Schools

S/No.	Item description	Mean	Std	Remark
1	I believe that sweeping in the night is sweeping your prosperity	3.51	0.64	Agree
2	I believe that traditional medicinal leaves are only cooked and taken with the left hand and not the right	3.47	0.74	Agree
3	I believe that female walking close to a dead dog or corpse may prevent them from bearing male children	3.54	0.62	Agree
4	I believe that if a child eats yellow yam, he/she will become dumb	3.30	0.99	Agree
5	Itchy palms are said to be a sign of good luck	3.60	0.64	Agree
6	I believe it is taboo to talk about parts of the reproductive system	3.46	0.80	Agree
7	I believe that an owl must not be seen in a daytime	3.41	0.77	Agree
8	I believe that if you have a sore throat, it is probably because you spat on the floor and someone stepped on it	3.47	0.81	Agree
9	I believe that whistling at night is believed to attract evil spirits	3.46	0.69	Agree
10	I believe that when your food falls to the ground you should not take it as the devil has taken it	2.54	0.93	Agree
Cluster mean		3.38		Agree

Data from Table 1 shows all the items have means above 2.50 which is the upper boundary decision rule. This means that respondents agreed that all the stated items are the perceived cultural practices believed by science students. The high cluster mean of 3.38 indicates that students agreed with that the stated cultural beliefs are perceived by them.

Research Question Two

What is the influence of perceived cultural beliefs on students' performance in science?

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Influence of Students Perceived Cultural Beliefs on their Performance in Science

S/No.	Item Description	Mean	Std	Remark
1	I believed that sweeping in the night does not influence my performance in science	3.46	0.63	HE
2	My cultural beliefs are against walking close to a dead dog will influence my performance in science	3.41	0.70	HE
3	My cultural beliefs are against whistling at night will influence my performance in science	3.30	0.72	HE
4	My cultural beliefs are against eating medicine with both hands influence my performance in science	3.30	0.84	HE
5	My cultural beliefs are against eating yellow yam does influence my performance in science	3.09	0.85	HE
6	My cultural beliefs that having a sore throat is probably because you spat on the floor and someone stepped on it. This will affect my academic performance in science	3.56	0.76	HE
7	I believe Seeing an owl in daytime will influence my performance in science	3.29	0.73	HE
8	My cultural beliefs are against talking about parts of the reproductive system influences my performance in science	3.47	0.62	HE
9	My cultural beliefs about not eating eggs will influence my performance in science	2.84	1.04	HE
10	My cultural beliefs are against killing a chameleon does not influence my performance in science	2.14	1.20	LE
Cluster mean		3.19		HE

Data from Table 2 shows that most respondents are of the view that the items on identified perceived cultural belief influence students' performance in science. The cluster mean of 3.19 above 2.50 which is the upper boundary decision rule shows that most respondents are of the view that the items on perceived cultural practices influence students' performance to a high extent.

Research Question Three

What is the difference in the influence of perceived cultural beliefs on male and female students' performance in science?

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Influence of Perceived Cultural Beliefs on Male and Female Students' Performance in Science

S/N	Item Description	Male		Rmk.	Female		Rmk.
		\bar{x}	δ		\bar{x}	δ	
1	I believed that sweeping in the night does not influence my performance in science	3.48	0.74	HE	3.40	0.50	HE
2	My cultural beliefs are against walking close to a dead dog will influence my performance in science	3.36	0.79	HE	3.50	0.57	HE
3	My cultural beliefs are against whistling at night will influence my performance in science	3.46	0.85	HE	3.38	0.58	HE
4	My cultural beliefs are against eating medicine with both hands influence my performance in science	3.50	0.93	HE	3.30	0.61	HE
5	My cultural beliefs are against eating yellow yams and do not influence my performance in science	3.11	0.97	HE	3.08	0.77	HE
6	My cultural beliefs that having a sore throat is probably because you spat on the floor, and someone stepped on it will affect my academic performance in science	3.55	0.88	HE	3.54	0.67	HE
7	I believe Seeing an owl in daytime will influence my performance in science	3.14	0.90	HE	3.44	0.70	HE
8	My cultural beliefs are against talking about parts of the reproductive system influences my performance in science	3.32	0.80	HE	3.56	0.69	HE
9	My cultural beliefs about not eating eggs will influence my performance in science	2.79	1.05	HE	3.00	0.98	HE
10	My cultural beliefs are against killing a chameleon does not influence my performance in science	2.24	1.10	LE	2.06	1.04	LE
	Cluster mean	3.20		HE	3.23		HE
	Mean diff	0.03					

The results from Table 3 indicate cluster means of 3.20 for male students and 3.23 for female students are all above 2.50 which is the upper boundary decision rule. The difference is 0.03 which is small difference indicating that the perceived cultural beliefs of male and female students are similar.

Hypothesis

Influence of perceived cultural beliefs on students' performance do not significantly differ between male and female students.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of Influence of Male and Female Students Perceived Cultural Beliefs on their Academic Performance in science

Gender	No.	X	δ	t-cal.	t-crit.	df.	Level of sig.
Male	66	3.20	0.83	1.50	1.66	115	0.05
Female	50	3.23	0.72				

From Table 5, t-cal. of 1.50 is less than t-crit. value of 1.66 at 115 degrees of freedom at Alpha level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. That means, the influence of students perceived cultural practices on their academic performance in science does not significantly differ between male and female students.

Discussion

The findings of the study are discussed based on the analysis of the research questions and hypothesis. The analysis of Research Question One in Table 1 shows that there are cultural practices in the study area which students believe in that inhibit science learning as indicated by 3.38 cluster mean response to the items. This agrees with the findings of Agogo and Onda (2014) as well as Adeniran and Yaapera (2019) which identified similar cultural practices which affect students learning of science. The study is predicated on the fact that science teachers do not know the cultural beliefs students bring into the science class. This was determined in this study as respondents agreed that all the stated items are their perceived cultural beliefs. This result connotes that despite the works of earlier researchers to address cultural practices and improve performance in the field of science education (Brumbach, Figueredo & Ellis, 2009; Taangahar & Ameh, 2017), there is still high level of cultural belief among science students which can lead to a persistent challenge of poor enrolment and performance in the sciences. This suggests that perception of science concepts arising from superstitious beliefs is to be countered immediately by science teachers during science lessons to prevent students' harboring anti-science cultural beliefs in science class.

The findings in Table 2 indicate that most respondents opined that cultural beliefs influence their performance to a high extent. The cluster mean of 3.19 shows that most respondents are of the view that the items on perceived cultural practices influence students' performance was to a high extent. This agrees with the findings of Akintoye and Saliu (2020) as well as Audu (2021) who opine that the perception students have on various cultural beliefs have great effect on students' performance in science. This implies that since the influence of cultural beliefs on performance is high it is important that teachers debunk misconstrued cultural beliefs among students when such science-inhibiting cultural beliefs are exhibited in class.

The study of gender was predicated on the need to determine whether the influence of perceived cultural beliefs was more on male or female science students. Ode *et al.* (2020). have earlier reported that cultural practices have significant influence on biology students'

performance based on gender. This corroborates with Ode *et al.*'s findings. Findings in Table 3 indicates that cultural practice has influence on male and female students' academic performance in science. The respondents in this study opined that cultural beliefs have influence on the performance of male and female students to a high extent (3.20 and 3.23 for males and females respectively). Even though the gender influence of perceived cultural beliefs on performance was high, its influence on female students was slightly more than that of male students with a mean difference of 0.03. This agrees with the findings of (Fatoki & Taangahar, 2019) as well as Akintoye and Saliu (2020) who view socio-cultural factors such as sex impact significantly on students' achievement in physics.

This result on gender was further affirmed by a t-test in Table 4 as the table value (1.66) was less than the calculated value (1.50). The findings of the study are also predicated on the fact that African traditional worldviews conflict with scientific explanation and understanding of natural phenomena. This suggests that science teachers have enormous tasks dealing with these misconceptions for effective understanding of scientific concepts. Ode *et al.*'s work provided a significant gender difference while this work has a slightly low in gender differential in favour of male which is not significant. Apart from countering and debunking these beliefs by science teachers, authors of science textbooks could adequately explain misconceived concepts in science for understanding of the concepts irrespective of gender.

Conclusion

Based on the findings it was concluded that perceived cultural beliefs highly influence the performance of science students in Makurdi Local Government Area and that there was no significant difference in the influence of perceived cultural beliefs on performance between male and female science students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that more awareness should be created to the students by science teachers so as to reduce the effect of cultural beliefs on their performance in science.

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